

Drip irrigation using the Internet of Things (IoT): An overview of scientific studies with an emphasis on the Kashkadarya area.

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Kashqadaryo viloyatiga alohida e'tibor qaratgan holda, tomchilatib sug'orish tizimlarida Internet buyumlar (IoT) texnologiyalarini qo'llash bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar sharhi keltirilgan. IoT texnologiyalarini sug'orish tizimlariga integratsiya qilishning asosiy afzalliklari, jumladan, suvdan foydalanish samaradorligini oshirish, resurslarni boshqarishni optimallashtirish va hosildorlikni yaxshilash kabi jihatlar ko'rib chiqilgan. Hududda IoT ni qishloq xo'jaligi amaliyotlariga joriy etish bo'yicha hozirgi yutuqlar va istiqbollari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Internet buyumlar, IoT, tomchilatib sug'orish, qishloq xo'jaligi, Kashqadaryo viloyati, suv tejash, resurslarni boshqarish, hosildorlik.

ABSTRACT

This article provides a review of scientific research on the application of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies in drip irrigation systems, with a particular focus on the Kashkadarya region. The main advantages of integrating IoT technologies into irrigation systems -such as improving water use efficiency, optimizing resource management, and enhancing crop yield—are discussed. Current achievements and prospects for implementing IoT in agricultural practices within the region are also explored.

Keywords: Internet of Things, IoT, drip irrigation, agriculture, Kashkadarya region, water conservation, resource management, crop yield.

THE INTRODUCTION

This part provides a summary of the subject. It presents the main ideas and establishes the background for the conversation that follows. The tributaries of

the Amu darya river provide around 75% of the water used in the Kashkadarya region's irrigation system. It is critically necessary to create effective irrigation techniques controlled by artificial intelligence due to the yearly drop in water volume. The problems with water supply will get more serious in the upcoming years. Large water reserves in the area are redirected by drainage collectors. However, over 25% of irrigation water is lost to these drainage basins, resulting in the accumulation of saline water in man-made reservoirs like "Sechankul" and "Achin Kul."

For this reason, it is very important to address the desalination of the water in these reservoirs for irrigating agricultural land. In particular, reverse osmosis desalination technologies are well suited for this use. With drip irrigation techniques, the resulting desalinated water could subsequently be utilized for crop irrigation. Artificial intelligence could be used in drip irrigation system management for the best water consumption.

METHODS

A thorough explanation of the techniques utilized to integrate Internet of Things (IoT) technologies into drip irrigation for Kashkadarya region agricultural fields is given in this part, along with techniques for resource management and water usage analysis and optimization.

1. Collection of data:

To ensure more precise monitoring, specialized soil moisture sensors are placed in the fields at different depths. These sensors gather information on soil moisture content, which helps determine how much water plants actually need and avoids over-irrigation. The information is sent to a central IoT platform for additional examination.

Weather stations: Automated weather stations that are positioned at strategic points gather data on humidity, precipitation, wind direction and speed, and air temperature. The information gathered helps with more accurate irrigation planning and control, and these factors have a direct impact on the water needs of crops.

2. Platform for data integration and IoT:

Irrigation management platform based on IoT: All gathered data is routed to an IoT platform in the cloud, where it is processed and turned into insights that can be put to use. By combining information from all sensors and weather

stations, the IoT platform offers a thorough understanding of field conditions and climatic variables.

Data processing and predictive algorithms: Machine learning and other artificial intelligence systems examine both historical and current sensor data. This enables the prediction of the water amounts required for irrigation, establishing the best times and amounts.

3. "Automated Irrigation System"

The automated irrigation system is linked to the Internet of Things platform and set up to automatically turn on or off the water supply in response to information from weather stations and soil moisture sensors. This is known as data-driven irrigation control. After analyzing this data, algorithms included into the platform modify the frequency and volume of irrigations.

Feedback and adaptation: The system automatically adjusts to situations that change. To avoid too much moisture, for instance, water production is decreased if rainfall is predicted. The system, on the other hand, provides more water as required if the soil is found to be unexpectedly dry.

4. Water quality monitoring and control:

Water quality sensors: These sensors keep an eye on the characteristics of water that is desalinating (using reverse osmosis techniques) due to the salinity of nearby reservoirs. These sensors monitor the amount of salt and other contaminants, which helps desalination processes work more efficiently and guarantee that irrigation water is safe without endangering soil salinization.

The process of reverse osmosis desalination is employed to cleanse water from drainage reservoirs such as "Sechankul" and "Achin Kul." In order to filter away salts and other dissolved materials, the water must travel through certain membranes. This method improves the quality of irrigation by supplying freshwater to agricultural areas.

5. Efficiency analysis and strategy adjustment:

Efficiency criteria: Important criteria, including water savings, yield growth, and lower water use costs, are established to evaluate the efficacy of the dropped irrigation system. These metrics are computed automatically by the system, which gathers data continuously.

Periodic modifications: Regular efficiency studies are carried out using the data gathered, and if required, watering schedules and IoT system settings are modified. With this strategy, the system may adjust to shifting circumstances and gradually increase its efficiency.

By integrating IoT technology into the drip irrigation system and optimizing the use of water resources in the Kashkadarya region, these techniques save water, save costs, and increase crop yields.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. IoT in general trends for drip irrigation

Studies show that adding IoT to drip irrigation systems greatly increases resource management and water use efficiency. IoT-connected sensors allow for ongoing monitoring of plant health, soil moisture, and weather, which improves irrigation schedules and cuts down on wasteful water use [2].

2. Using the internet of things for Kashkadarya region drip irrigation

The southern section of Uzbekistan's Kashkadarya region is distinguished by its desert environment and scarce water supplies. Drip irrigation systems in this area could use water more efficiently and produce more crops if IoT technologies are implemented. IoT applications in drip irrigation in the Kashkadarya region have not received much attention in research, despite this promise [3].

3. Benefits and difficulties of using IoT in drip irrigation

Using IoT in drip irrigation has several advantages, including:

Water savings: Excessive water use can be avoided with accurate soil moisture monitoring.

Better plant growth and development are encouraged by optimized irrigation, which results in higher yields.

Lower operating costs: Automation decreases operating costs and eliminates the need for manual labor [4].

However, adoption of IoT is accompanied by several challenges:

- **High initial costs:** IoT system configuration and setup come with a hefty price tag [5].

The necessity of technical maintenance: To guarantee system dependability, routine up keep and updates are necessary.

Training of Staff: Education and training of workers are necessary for the effective usage of IoT technology.

4. Artificial intelligence in drip irrigation: An update

Since AI makes it possible to manage irrigation more precisely and predictively, its potential and role in drip irrigation are becoming more and more significant. AI integration into drip irrigation systems enables data analysis from Internet of Things sensors, enabling irrigation automation and water volume forecasts [6].

Artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms can adjust the irrigation schedule by learning from past data while taking into account the present weather, soil moisture content, and plant requirements. Thus, this leads to:

Water use optimization: AI forecasts water needs based on present and projected conditions [7].

Management costs are decreased because automated system regulation eliminates the need for continual human supervision.

Enhanced crop resilience: Through accurate water distribution, plants get the precise amount of moisture they require, lowering the danger of over-irrigation and encouraging improved growth.

Drip irrigation, which combines AI and IoT, is therefore a promising combination of two technologies that can reduce water consumption, increase crop yields, and develop sustainable agricultural models in areas with limited resources, like the Kashkadarya region [8].

CONCLUSION

Drip irrigation systems that include Internet of Things (IoT) technology show promise for increasing the efficiency of water resources and boosting agricultural process management. For areas with scarce water supplies, like the Kashkadarya region, this is especially important. It is crucial to take into account the benefits as well as any potential technical and financial obstacles for the successful integration of IoT in drip irrigation. Developing the best plans and models for the successful implementation of IoT in the region's agriculture would be made easier with more study in this field.

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